

Fig S9. Comparison of local motion kymographs of simulated polarized cell tracks for different temporal resolutions: $\delta t \in \{0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 2.5, 3.\bar{3}\}$. In the top left corner, the center of mass trajectory (colored lines) and the trace of each cell track (gray area) are displayed. In the top right corner, the contour dynamics (colored lines) and the trace of the cell track (gray area) are shown. Below, kymographs of the local motion based on our model are listed for each cell track.